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Redefining Black Female Identity: A Study of Gloria Naylor's *Bailey's Cafe*

Dr Karunesh
Associate Professor,
Department of English,
Government P.G. College, Sector 1,
Panchkula, Haryana.

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Abstract:

The hegemonic value system continues to generate destructive images of Black women even in the modern times only to prevent them from forming an independent identity. The African-American women have suffered a lot due to these stereotyped negative and controlling images constructed by the white racist society. These images hide the complexities and ambiguities, the challenges and the joys experienced by black women in their real lives. With the experiences of strained familial relationships, poor educational histories and bleak employment records, they face the problem of defending their self-regulating Black identity. Rejection of these images can liberate them from the confinement of double oppression of racism and sexism. In their journey towards self-definition, African-American women get help from different sources, but the chief origin of undergoing alteration remains within their own consciousness. The paper focuses on the struggle of six black female personages who despite all the soul-scorching experiences in their lives, strive hard to discard the derogatory labels and to redefine themselves in their own way.

Keywords: Patriarchal, conformity, predicament, sexuality, conscience, womanhood.

Introduction

Gloria Naylor (1950-2016), a strong African American voice of the contemporary period, explores the idea of defying boundaries and discarding labels in her fourth novel *Bailey's Cafe* (1992). The novel depicts the predicament of six black female personages, their struggle and their survival in the face of still-alive racism. They have been exploited in various ways in an ever-threatening and impersonal world of white supremacy. They have been mistreated by their parents, betrayed by their brothers, husbands and sons, beaten up, abandoned and even branded by men. Naylor skillfully dramatizes the individual lives of black women whose individuality is threatened by stifling, damaging and even destructive forces prevalent in the affluent American society. The author explores the extremes of social horrors which befall these women: from the blatant and hackneyed ideas of forced prostitution to the enslaving quality of rigid social definitions, the ever-deferred American dream, the withholding of alternatives, the trap of ingrained conformity, and patriarchal notions of good and evil.

In the novel, the Cafe run by Nadine and Bailey, can better be called a “halfway house” positioned between the edge of the world and infinite possibility. It represents the uncharted precincts of an ingenious consciousness that is definitely both black and female. The Cafe becomes the setting for the whole novel in which Black women from different births and backgrounds enter to voice their sufferings. As Karen Joy Fowler says, “Geographically Bailey’s Cafe is everywhere. It can be entered from the real world at any point; its address is despair” (Fowler 26). The Cafe can be a tranquilizer for the black women to relieve them of the pains received from the sexist and racist society for a prolonged period.

Patriarchal constructions of the cult of true womanhood make it imperative that White men and women view Black women as wanton whores and their offspring as objects of jest. The images of Black women constructed by the white society over the centuries have retained a negative characterization of Black sexuality. Their individual self is totally crushed because of the behaviour and value system of the dominant culture. As Naylor states, “The Core of the work is indeed the way in which the word *whore* has been used against women or to manipulate female sexual identity” (Fowler 150).

In the first chapter, Naylor employs a systematic and thorough deconstruction of the damning label of whore by creating the most innocent and loving character Sadie. As an unwanted child born by accident, she grows up in an environment bereft of love, compassion and care, “The One The Coat Hanger Missed” (Naylor 41). When her mother shows no love for Sadie and beats her mercilessly, she thinks that it must be her fault and tries to be very good to please her mother. She is so obsessed with the thought of pleasing her mother that she dreams:

There was to be a trim white bungalow with a green picket fence, and she would keep the front yard swept clean of leaves and pick all the withered blooms from their fence full of roses. She would go to the academy ... starched white collar and black ribbon tie ... Mama, I'm doing so good here. Yes, I'm so proud of you. You're a good girl, Sadie. (Naylor 44)

Unfortunately, Sadie is never able to please her mother and her world of dreams shatters when she is forced into prostitution by her own mother at the age of thirteen. The final blow to Sadie comes with her marriage to Daniel, a man thirty years her older who constantly humiliates and suspects her, “He mistrusted her eyes... Her cleaning irritated him... And he suspected that

she couldn't have child because she'd caught some white man's disease in the white whorehouse” (53-54).

Born into the world of oppression and exploitation that fits the conventional definition of whore, Sadie internalizes dominant cultural standards of behaviour and values that lead her to ultimate self-destruction. She stumbles into prostitution to keep her house, failing which she turns to alcohol to preserve her dream house and again to prostitution to buy the alcohol she depends upon. The brutality of her life has pushed her so deep into the well that her dreams of a house, a picket fence, germaniums, laughter, waterford crystal and good meal become so disconnected from reality that she cannot accept Iceman Jones' offer of a shared life. She wants to keep all her dreams intact so that she may remain whole.

Sadie's life is a tragic example of a life destroyed by adherence to dominant cultural dreams. Bailey and Nadine try to recognise the lady within the whore as they see the miracle in the hands of Sadie when “the thick mug had lost its cracks and stains, hitting the tabletop with the ring of china, while the bent tin spoon and paper napkin became monogrammed silver and linen” (Naylor 40). With the help of Nadine and Eve, Sadie and Jones dance under the stars, and she smiles and has “her first real kiss” (Naylor 76).

By presenting Sadie's story, Naylor insists on the incorruptibility of the innocent and pure, for Sadie's innate moral sensibility remains intact long after her mind has been destroyed. Her story presents the survival strategies of the prototype of the unwanted and unloved child who believes that she is not loved because she is not good. She is a person wronged by all; however, she possesses the sweetest and most unprotesting of spirits. Though she is a wino and a twenty-five-cent whore, she desires neither men nor money. The complexity of her character forces the

reader to rethink the construction of female sexuality present in the larger society. Indeed the derogatory label of whore hung on one such as Sadie loses its virulence, its damning connotations crumbling into dust, successfully deconstructed.

The next section “Eve’s Song” deals with the story of Eve – the proprietor of boarding house in the neighbourhood of Bailey’s Cafe. She is brought up by a preacher whom she calls Godfather. He provides her shelter and sustenance in exchange for total obedience. Eve is forced to live a life of isolation. A chance discovery of eroticism of the earth's tremors against her body awakens her sexuality and she comes to the recognition of her oneness with the earth. When confronted by her tyrannical Godfather about an exciting game she plays with Billy Boy– a boy with an infant's brain–she is expelled from the church for the heinous crime of enjoying sensations and sensualities derived from the earth and her body. She is driven into the delta, hungry and naked. This inhuman treatment forces her to take a long journey from Pilottown to Louisiana with a hope to survive. Montgomery says:

Perhaps the most definitive change in Eve’s evolving consciousness occurs when she comes to recognise his church as a social construct reflecting the hierarchies of a society which relegates women to undesirable position of subservient “other”.
(Montgomery 28)

When Eve recognises that “there was nowhere on earth for a woman like me” she returns to the earth and becoming a creature of the earth enters New Orleans “neither male nor female – mud” (Naylor 91). After reaching Bailey’s Cafe, she makes a boarding house for the women who are down and out. At the back of the Cafe, she helps these women realise their dreams before they come to stay at her boarding house. Eve commits herself to empowering women who are

rendered powerless by the circumstances and tries to teach them survival rather than pure transcendence. She helps them claim their right to selfhood by inverting the dreams that once bound them.

With the recreation of Eve as a strong but sensitive woman, Naylor seems to suggest that in order to redefine and recreate female identity, it is necessary to go beyond the confines of society and culture that delimit the potential of women by attaching derogatory labels to them. The rejection of the derogatory and controlled images of mammies, conjurers, whores etc., paves the way for freedom from the confinements of double oppression of racism and patriarchy. As Collins asserts, "Resisting by doing something that 'is not expected' could not have occurred without Black women's long-standing rejection of mammies, matriarchs, and other controlling images" (Collins 98).

Throughout the stories of these women, what echoes is female subjectivity to male desires. If Sadie was only thirteen when her mother pushed her into prostitution, Esther was only twelve when her brother bartered her to an older, propertied farmer in exchange for higher share cropping wages. Without resistance she surrenders to the whims of the landlord who chooses to be intimate with her only in the cellar of his home. Initially, she is too young to understand this, but gradually, the reality dawns upon her. She becomes so depressed that she can exist only in the darkness of a basement at Eve's, where her only companions are the spiders and a radio. Her monologues point to a profound self-hatred in a world that evolves no terms for her existence:

I like the white roses because they show up in the dark.

I don't.

The black gal.Monkey face.Tar.Coal.Ugly.Soot.

Unspeakable.Pitch.Coal.Ugly.Soot.Unspeakable.” (Naylor 95)

Esther’s hatred for men becomes so intense that she thinks of killing the landlord when she is about to leave the place in order to save “other young girls waiting in line to sleep alone in his pink-and-lace bed.... But my guess turned out to be right. There are too many of them to kill. And there are just too many twelve-year-olds” (Naylor 99). The repeated incidents of rape and sexual perversions force Esther to take refuge in the insanity and the darkness of Eve’s cellar. By demanding white Christmas roses from her gentleman callers at Eve’s, who must call her *little sister*, Esther relieves her painful past.

Through this tale of Sweet Esther, who has “the most honest face for any women” (Naylor 99), Naylor exposes the chilling callousness of male relations who hold their women in so little worth. They are not even consulted before making them sex slaves for the sake of others. The commodification of poor, little black girls for the sake of material gains exposes the ugly face of the patriarchal society that objectifies women only for the sake of material advancement without taking into consideration the enormity of their suffering and sacrifice.

While Esther fancies herself too ugly to be loved, Peaches, the beautiful protagonist of the next story “Mary (Take One)”, suffers due to the damning image attached to the African-American women. As she grows up, her father’s over-zealous possessiveness to protect her from the males of all ages, gives her a muted message that invariably shapes her personality to fit an age-old-mould. Wherever she goes, people look at her lustfully and want her physically. The poor girl finds herself unable to understand her true self. Men’s eyes appear like mirrors to her:

Every mirror outside had told me what she was: the brown mirrors, hazel mirrors,
blue mirrors, oval, round, and lashed mirrors of all their eyes when they looked at

me. Old eyes, young eyes, it didn't make any difference if the mirrors belonged to men. (Naylor 104)

Peaches finds herself torn between two images, “a whore and ... Daddy's baby” (Naylor 104). She ultimately attempts to reconcile her external and internal self by destroying her physical beauty, which is the real cause of her suffering: “First, I took the tip of the beer opener, smiled into the mirror, and traced the path I was going to take I grasped the opener in both hands and dug down” (Naylor 111).

Naylor exposes the danger awaiting those who depend on the approval of others for generating self-love and attempt to fit themselves into the male-defined categories of saint or sinner. The writer reiterates her message that women must learn to value themselves without using the currency of their desirability to men. There is a need to reconstruct a positive self-image which proclaims that black is beautiful, not only outwardly but inwardly as well. After reaching Bailey's Cafe, Peaches transforms her damaged image into a beautiful unified whole. Eve's eyes mirror the beginning of this process:

Gently she removed my veil, and she lifted my chin in her hands to trace her thumb down along the path I had taken in front of the mirror. I saw only scar reflected in her rimless glasses as she felt each jagged curve, each section of twisted flesh. And it was only the scar that was reflected in her eyes when she murmured, Beautiful. (Naylor 112)

Eve's restoration of selfhood holds much promise. By setting the prices of Peaches' daffodils high and demanding that she accepts only the 'freshest' of flowers, Eve weeds out the

men who still wish to objectify her and works towards the discovery of a single man who will be able to understand her real value as a dignified human being.

Naylor exposes the psychological and social damage caused by black acceptance of white middle-class values through the story of Jesse Bell, a woman who is proud of her cultural heritage. She is married into the King family of Harlem's Sugar Hill where Uncle Eli wields a strange power over the people telling them what to eat, what to wear and what to laugh about. He is so conscious of white people and their thoughts about them that he wants to lift the race according to the white standards. Jesse refuses to subscribe to the snobbery and contempt of Uncle Eli's doctrines as she believes, "to raise something, you gotta first it as being low-down. And I didn't see a damn thing wrong with being colored. And where did Uncle Eli want us to be lifted up to?" (Naylor 125).

Jesse has to pay a heavy price for not adopting the values taught by Uncle Eli, who is a shrewd person and always conspires against her. He is determined to finish her by ostracizing her from her husband and King family. Jesse refuses to be ashamed of the people and culture she loves so desperately and fights against Uncle Eli's useless doctrines of imitating white people. She cleverly uses all the weapons at her disposal, including her strength of personality and her sexuality, to draw her husband to an understanding of her and a mutual enjoyment of her traditions. The diabolic Uncle Eli, with his shrewd plans, strips her of her family and the life she knew and also takes the good name in which she had such pride, and "the name of Jesse Bell came to mean that no-good slut from the docks" (Naylor 131).

Jesse comes to the realization that Uncle Eli's revenge was to nullify her as thoroughly as possible. Failing to "figure out how it all happened? When had it happened.... When had

Uncle Eli killed me in my own home? When? And what had he used? (Naylor 130), she gives herself to drinking and drugs. After a short detention in anti-drug cell, Jesse reaches Bailey's Cafe where Eve helps her in every possible way to give up the habit of addiction to heroin and accept the reality in order to survive. Eve succeeds in showing her that there is still hope for her and that all is not over yet. Jesse seeks alternative means of self-affirmation as she refuses to entertain anyone, and those "who try to visit her get their flowers smashed right in their faces at the door short" (Naylor 116). She rejects others' definitions of her and reclaims a life of her own.

Naylor seems to question the extent to which Black people have lost their blackness, which is an essential part of their personalities to make them unique. She warns the black community against submitting to the white hegemony and their longing to be acceptable to the larger white community. The author suggests that black people should be proud of their rich culture and heritage. 'Black is beautiful' is not only a slogan but a realizable ideal for black people in general and black women in particular to live by in the American milieu.

"Mary (Take Two)" is a heart-rending portrayal of the sufferings of a fourteen-year-old Ethiopian girl Mariam, who is pregnant without involving herself into any sexual act. She is expelled from her village as she is unable to reveal the name of the man responsible for her pregnancy. She keeps repeating, "No man has ever touched me" (Naylor 143). Mariam has also gone through the painful experience of Circumcision – a rite of passage designed solely for girls to raise their value and increase their marital prospects. She suffers due to the cruel patriarchal system that robs her of her health and potential for sexuality, only to form her body into a message to her future husband that no man has been there before him.

With the help of Gibbs Mariam is sent to the boarding house where Eve finds no reason to blame Mariam for her pregnancy and arranges the dream setting for her: “The Eucalyptus trees. The Juniper. A steep-sloping mountain in the background. The air drifting from the back smelled like damp moss and thin lines of sunshine filtered in under the doorjamb (Naylor 224). The birth of little George is miraculous as he is not only the first-born in the neighbourhood, but also born to a virgin. By presenting the tragic conditions of these black women, Naylor brings into light the horror story of all oppressed women who have been exploited by patriarchal forces from the creation of Eve to the modern era.

Bailey underscores the arbitrariness of labels by admitting that his real name is not Bailey and the Cafe is not even his. In the same way, his wife Nadine rejects the preconceptions of the standard behaviour and demands that her uniqueness must be accepted. She does not allow anybody to define her personality by assessing her superficially. When Bailey questions her on her constant refusal to smile, she retorts back, saying: “What does that have to do with being pleased?... I am more than my body, she finally said” (Naylor17-18). Bailey admits that this reaction of his wife taught him a crucial lesson of life and changed his way of looking at her as well as the other women, contrary to the established norms of the society. Wilson underscores the importance of the person rather than the label attached:

More important is the fact that the symbol is less important than the signified.

That is, in this case the person underneath the label is more important than the label. But in order to appreciate this fact, one must be willing to get to know the person and not be influenced, or even discouraged, by the mere label. (Wilson135).

Despite all the odds and adversities, Naylor's women try to redefine their own identity by fighting back in their own way. Eve recreates herself by mustering her strength and acts as a mother figure for all women who have nowhere to go. Her willingness to sell all of her other flowers except lilies seems to suggest that her sexuality belongs only to her, to be defined in her own way. Her boarders also assert themselves by demanding the freshest flowers of their choice from the gentlemen callers. They nurture a sense of self-esteem and in turn find their lost identity. As Fowler states:

Beginning with the nurturance of self-esteem that comes with each bouquet of flowers, Eve helps her boarders learn their own worth and, in the process, escape from the bondage of dominant cultural dreams that have limited their development. (Fowler 125)

At Eve's boarding house, these crushed women generate the hope for necessary living and reclaim a life of their own. This is the place where all these women celebrate the birth of Mariam's son, George. Jesse hurls her skirt, Esther laughs and Peaches sings with her sweet voice. In a collective voice, they tell the newly born not to feel ashamed of his illegitimate birth and also convey a clear message to the hegemonic powers that God is the father of all human beings. They should be treated equally irrespective of their race, class and gender.

Conclusion

Thus, Naylor in *Bailey's Cafe* tries to deconstruct the negative image of *whore* attached to African-American women by highlighting the lives of her innocent women characters who suffer only because of their innocent nature which demands constant approval from others. They have suffered rejection and failure that might have crushed a lesser person. Despite all the adversities,

these women refuse to be defined exclusively in terms of their bodies and strive to find the means of asserting their female identity. By elevating themselves to a position of power these black women directly challenge the racial and patriarchal forces which try to delimit their potential by attaching damning labels to their female identity. Naylor explores the possibilities of healing the black community affected by the interrelationship of race, class and gender in the women like Eve and Nadine, who not only assert their own female identity but also help other women of their community to recreate and redefine their female identity.

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